

EELISA

European University

EELISA INNOCORE

Deliverable 1.4 Policy brief

Date: 31 May 2024

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

1 Feedback on progress

This document represents an update of D1.3 Policy brief (1). D1.3 included an analysis of the challenges encountered by EELISA InnoCORE during the first half of the project regarding collaboration in the R&I dimension of the Alliance. Some of those challenges are still relevant, namely:

- The *involvement of permanent administrative staff beyond the core teams* remains a challenge (by 'core teams' we refer to individuals and managers specifically appointed to EELISA InnoCORE). As explained in D1.5 Cost-Benefit Analysis, EELISA InnoCORE actions managed to create well-functioning **communities of practice** beyond the core teams (e.g. communities of practice of tech transfer experts, open science experts, librarians, EU policy and funding experts, gender equality experts). However, as indicated in D1.3, it is also true that the involvement of people beyond the core teams comes at the expense of "stretching human resources at its maximum" (see D1.3 and refer to the recommendations below). This issue is still standing.
- The question of *approaching external stakeholders* has progressed still relatively slowly for the same reasons as pointed out in D1.3. EELISA partners are reluctant "to contact industry and the private sector without having first a clear portfolio of what EELISA and its different projects can offer" (D1.3), and building a strong, clear, and unified portfolio still needs more time. EELISA InnoCORE has taken, though, some important steps forward in this direction, particularly during the II R&I symposium —which was dedicated to the topic of industrial PhDs and industrial chairs— and the work done for the nomination of the 1st EELISA Industrial Chair.

Please describe the **challenges** your Alliance encountered regarding cooperation between universities in the field of R&I in relation to the institutional change areas (transformation modules) foreseen.

Here, we list some new challenges that EELISA partners encountered during its second half.

(i) The challenge of having different governance structures and levels of autonomy, different legal frameworks and procedures, combined with the need of balancing the autonomy of individual institutions with the need of centralized coordination (all ITMs, particularly 1 and 3).

The governance of universities and their ways of working are subject to many different aspects and layers, from national, regional, and local laws to European frameworks, as well as their own internal rules. The institutional autonomy of universities is a core principle that governs our universities. Moreover, in the case of EELISA, its partner universities are highly diverse in terms of size and nature. This means that under EELISA, nine (and since November 2022 ten) institutions with different leadership and organizational methods, various idiosyncrasies, and subject to very different legal schemes, joined forces to create new opportunities and to develop joint policies, resources and instruments. **The enormous variety of rules, procedures and legal frameworks combined with the need of balancing autonomy with centralized coordination have been major challenges** under almost all ITMs, very particularly those developing joint policies.

For instance, EELISA InnoCORE partners defined some basic rules for accessing infrastructures — researchers from other EELISA institutions will be considered internal users (declaration of intent)—, but the reality is that access to infrastructures varies significantly and establishing common rules represents a main challenge. Whereas some partners have a fixed regulation and prize setting policy for accessing infrastructures (such as UPM), others do not have a global policy and decisions on price-setting lies completely on the responsible researchers managing the infrastructures. Some partners make the distinction between different types of users (internal and external users, external academic users and non-academic users), but not all partners make this differentiation. Moreover, when working on defining a process for developing joint infrastructures, it became clear that another layer of autonomy had to be taken into account: **the autonomy of researchers**. Except in some cases where the acquisition of a certain infrastructure is considered strategic by the university, in general terms, the setup of research infrastructures is mostly a bottom-up process relying on proposals stemming directly from the research structures who are the managers of the infrastructure. Given that the decision on the infrastructures to be developed is not a centralized process, defining joint rules or a joint roadmap became major challenges. Moreover, the funding opportunities for infrastructures are very limited,

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

mainly local, and sharing ownership poses many legal problems difficult to overcome (liabilities, covering expenses related to maintenance or consumables, insurance).

As another example, EELISA InnoCORE partners agreed on a joint protocol for the nomination of EELISA Industrial Chairs in September 2023. The goal of industrial chairs being the same, i.e., to foster collaboration with industry, EELISA partners implement the concept in very different ways. Whereas for some partners the concept refers to an individual (model used by partners such as BME), for other partners it is an agreement between the university and a company (model used by partners such as FAU, ENPC or UPM). Fitting together different concepts was highly difficult. The protocol was subject to intense negotiations among strategic contacts and reaching consensus proved arduous. Moreover, partners are aware that **the actual implementation of the concept will bring to the surface new challenges and possible flaws, including potential clashes with regional legislation (FAU endorsed the protocol and agreed on its piloting at EELISA level while pointing out to potential legal barriers to overcome if an EELISA Industrial Chair was to be created and hosted by FAU due to Bavarian laws)**. Lastly, it might be the case that EELISA partners have a chair with the same company (local branch of a company): this overlap, although pointing out to similarities, brings new challenges regarding compliance with different laws or different aims of the agreements and goals of the chair.

Lastly, regarding the challenge of having different legal frameworks and organizational structures, another layer of complexity is to be added when it comes to universities from non-European countries, subject to even more different legal frameworks, cultural and organizational structures.

(ii) The challenge of fully exploiting the tools within the timeframe of the project together with the challenge of sustainability (all ITMs).

In the Policy Brief D1.3, EELISA InnoCORE partners highlighted the challenge of creating the right incentives for the engagement of research and teaching staff. Since November 2022, EELISA InnoCORE has put in place a whole array of incentives and tools, such as the EELISA Connect call for workshops, the EELISA InnoCORE networking platform or the EELISA Next Level event. As the cost-benefit analysis revealed (refer to D1.5), these initiatives have brought important benefits to the Alliance and met their goals of connecting researchers and innovators. EELISA InnoCORE can assert that the challenge mentioned in D1.3 has been successfully addressed. However, new challenges arose: **how to keep the momentum, how to further exploit the contacts created and meet expectations once the EELISA InnoCORE project ends?** EELISA 2.0 has been designed so that the work done under InnoCORE is not lost and can be continued. However, giving the different nature and scope of the projects (Erasmus+ vs. Horizon Europe), the sustainability of some initiatives is still a concern.

Another challenge related to the tools and instruments created, such as the catalogue of infrastructures, the EELISA InnoCORE Networking Platform, the open science training hub or the protocol for the nomination of industrial chairs, has been the limited time available for fully deploying them. The open science training hub was launched not long ago, the catalogue of facilities is still facing some IT difficulties and the nomination of the 1st industrial chair only happened in December 2023—it has to be noted that the term of the industrial chair is two years. All of them are very complex initiatives and their development took very important resources and time. **EELISA InnoCORE did not offer a sufficient timeframe to complete what we could consider a whole management cycle—development, launching, gathering speed and critical mass, monitoring and evaluation.** Some initiatives are still in what we could call testing phase and did not reach enough maturity.

Having an effective communication is also critical for the success of any action. It goes without saying that reaching the relevant target group—be it researchers, innovators, administrative staff, the higher ranks of our institutions, society, policymakers, private companies, venture capital investors, NGOs, associations, public organizations—and have them on board, using the tools created, is the key for success. Here again autonomy and coordination need to coexist: EELISA central communication channels need to be coordinated and combined with the individual dissemination and communication channels of our institutions, where EELISA must share space with other initiatives. Maintaining clear channels of communication and managing information flows is not always a straightforward task.

(iii) The challenge of digitalisation and digitation of resources.

In the Policy Brief D1.3, EELISA InnoCORE partners pointed out to the digitalisation and digitation of resources as a main challenge that the Alliance was facing. The challenges pointed out therein are not only valid (e.g. the challenge of the interoperability among the individual partner’s IT tools), but some new ones appeared, particularly regarding the interoperability of the tools created under InnoCORE with those created under EELISA. To guarantee the homogeneity of the IT tools and platforms created, avoid duplications and facilitate the long-term sustainability of the tools, EELISA decided that all the IT developments created under InnoCORE would be integrated within the IT tools developed under EELISA, particularly the EELISA community platform¹. This refers very concretely to those tools that require a log-in. The EELISA community platform includes a log-in functionality based on EduGain for staff from EELISA universities, therefore, it was decided to use this same platform and login functionality for EELISA InnoCORE tools requiring identification (the networking platform and the catalogue of infrastructures). The mismatch between the two projects with different timeframes, the different partners leading the tasks and the changes in lead beneficiaries, the **different suppliers developing the tools**—both the EINP and the catalogue of infrastructures were developed by external providers via a tender, as specified in the Grant Agreement— created difficulties (some still pending, see below).

(iv) The challenge of mainstreaming open science (OS) practices.

Under EELISA InnoCORE, EELISA partners developed a common OS framework and methodological toolkit that partners used to develop or update their individual OS action plans. As revealed by D1.5 C&B analysis, this action has brought very positive benefits to the Alliance and is highly considered by partners. However, partners still stress that mainstreaming open science faces many challenges within our institutions: tensions between the existing research assessment practices and the new OS paradigm (indeed, many researchers are accustomed to the traditional publishing models and are hesitant to embrace open science), current incentive structures in academia that still prioritize traditional publishing metrics, lack of knowledge, skills, and understanding not only by researchers but also by university leaders.

Please **describe how you tackled or intend to tackle these challenges**. Based on your project’s experience so far (and if applicable), briefly outline case(s) that you consider as good practice and of interest to other universities or to policy-makers

Challenge	How EELISA partners are tackling the challenge
Different governance structures and levels autonomy, different legal frameworks and procedures	Negotiation, coordination, and compromise are the only ingredients for tackling this challenge. EELISA InnoCORE partners decided to reach, as a first step, flexible and basic agreements based on the good will of partners (e.g. for the rules of access), and pilot the agreements, being aware that new challenges will arise with the implementation.
Short-term nature of InnoCORE vs. sustainability of the actions	<p>Since its inception, EELISA 2.0 was built taking into account InnoCORE work. Some of the most successful initiatives in InnoCORE will continue, with the proper adjustments, under EELISA WP9 EELISA’s Network for Researchers and Talent (networking platform, page ‘Opportunities for young researchers’, catalogue of facilities, OS training hub, PLB) and EELISA WP10 EELISA Innovation & Entrepreneurship Ecosystems (Entrepreneurship School, Prototype Contest, Next Level event). D1.5 C&B analysis will be fundamental in guiding this process.</p> <p>EELISA Communities are proving to be very good channels for keeping the networking of experts and building communities of practice outside the limits of the projects. EELISA Communities are fully bottom-up initiatives that any person related to EELISA can promote (researchers, students, staff, etc.). There is an EELISA community on open science born out of the work of InnoCORE WP3, one for research managers born out the work of InnoCORE Policy Liaisons Board, one on entrepreneurship born out of Unfolds and InnoCORE WP7.</p>

¹ <https://community.eelisa.eu/>

<p>Digitalisation and digitation of resources</p>	<p>Again, EELISA 2.0 will be the key in tackling this issue. The problem of digitalisation and digitation of resources had been identified by EELISA and InnoCORE (D1.3) and the new EELISA WP4 Whole EELISA European Campus is meant to address digitalization and IT tools in a homogenised and comprehensive manner. (Regarding InnoCORE platforms, the networking platform is fully functioning and integrated in the EELISA communities' platform since September 2023. For the catalogue of infrastructures, the IT team is working on solving some still pending problems regarding the login functionality).</p>
<p>Mainstreaming open science practices</p>	<p>In addition to the OS toolkit, EELISA InnoCORE has put in place other initiatives to address the different angles of this challenge: a) a network of OS ambassadors, OS champions that set the example; b) an OS training hub to address the lack of skills.</p>
<p>Creating the right incentives for the engagement of researchers (challenge from D1.3)</p>	<p>EELISA InnoCORE addressed this challenge with quite success via a full set of initiatives and tools: the EELISA Connect call for workshops, the EINP, the different innovation and entrepreneurship competitions (EELISA Prototype Contests, EELISA Next Level event). The opening up of already existing activities, giving them an EU dimension, has proved particularly successful.</p>
<p>Approaching external stakeholders (challenge from D1.3)</p>	<p>InnoCORE has taken some steps to build connections with non-academic partners at EELISA level, this has been done particularly via the work regarding industrial chairs, the R&I symposium, and the involvement of venture capital investors in the EELISA Next Level event, as well as indirectly via D5.5 Digital Innovation Hubs.</p>

Please describe the **tangible progress** that individual partners as well as the Alliance as a whole have made in terms of introducing changes in their entities as a result of this project. Please elaborate on whether the inclusive and integrated cooperation approach of your alliance helps accelerate institutional change of all partners (e.g. through sharing of practices from institutions with strong expertise or infrastructure in specific areas to institutions without).

Below you will find a figure summarizing InnoCORE's main tangible progress:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

2 Policy recommendations

EELISA InnoCORE partners would like to refer the reader to the **Policy Brief D1.3 whose recommendations are still fully valid**. EELISA InnoCORE partners would like to highlight the relevance of the recommendations included in the previous policy brief and reassert their support to those messages. Below we include some new ideas from the debates held.

Policy topic 1: Facilitating transnational cooperation

Knowing that the Commission proposed a [Council recommendation to facilitate transnational collaboration between universities](#), which action should be prioritised to address the challenges you encountered as an Alliance in sharing capacities, infrastructures, resources or staff in R&I?

Policy topic 4: Access to excellence

What is your advice on how to accelerate access to excellence in science and in value creation for all participants for higher education institutions across the entire ERA, through the European Universities Initiative?

Reinforce local permanent structures. European Alliances have set up central teams coordinating the work of the different partners and offering some joint services. At EELISA, the EELISA central office is now supported by EELISA Local Offices at each partner institution (ELOs). ELOs are made of both people fully dedicated to the project, hired exclusively for the project, as well as of **experts on the different topics, normally permanent staff (civil servants) with a long track record in the host institution, who have been assigned to EELISA and now dedicate part of their time to the Alliance**. As lengthily explained in former documents (see D1.3) and above, the involvement of the permanent staff is critical for the success of any action put in place by the Alliance. However, their involvement has also created a very heavy workload for some staff, sometimes difficult to manage. **Reinforcing local structures and resources within universities will be the only way for tackling this growing workload in the long term.** Although this claim might lie beyond the control of the European Union, EELISA partners would like to highlight the **need of reinforcing universities permanent human resources, including both academic and non-academic staff**, as a prerequisite for facilitating transnational cooperation and raising excellence.

Pilot call for putting in place an internal funding programme. In addition to the recommendations already put forward in D1.3, EELISA InnoCORE partners think that it might be worth piloting a call to deploy Alliance-level research funding programmes to foster collaboration among researchers. The idea would be to have enough resources and the right call framework to put in place an Alliance, inter-Alliance or consortium-level research funding programme similar to what Spanish universities call *programa propio* (internal programme) and similar to what EELISA is doing with the joint calls and InnoCORE did with the EELISA Connect call for workshops. This would be a **joint R&I cascade funding programme for researchers** of the consortium promoting different aspects: A) Talent attraction, growth and consolidation (e.g. via research visits); B) Internationalization (e.g. small research collaborative projects, funding for organization of joint events); C) Promotion of the acquisition and upgrade of SciTech infrastructures; D) Mobility; E) Prizes. Some of these initiatives have already been tested (e.g. EELISA Connect call). The aim would be to test during some years the implementation of a bigger programme made of regular calls.

Keep working on ensuring equitable access to research facilities, funding mobility and training programmes to attract and retain top talent and support gender equality, diversity and inclusion in STEM. EELISA InnoCORE partners would like to recall the following paragraph from their position paper on Horizon Europe:

“EELISA partners highly appreciate the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation as a powerful tool boosting their internationalization, helping them deepen, widen and diversify collaborations with other international partners as well as with industrial stakeholders. Participating in EU projects increases the visibility and recognition of EELISA researchers in the international academic field, EU projects providing academics with an opportunity to cooperate with other institutions and peers all around the world and thus boosting their international prestige. EELISA partners value R&I programmes also as way

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

to attract international talent and increase the impact of their research activities, including bringing research closer to society. Within this context, the EU R&I programmes represent a fundamental and indispensable tool for EELISA institutions”.

In line with this, **EELISA InnoCORE partners reiterate their support to the ERA building process and to the different EU R&I programmes as a way of boosting cohesion** and having fairer societies. To achieve this, EELISA InnoCORE partners encourage the European Commission to keep supporting projects and programmes for: a) ensuring equitable access to research equipment, laboratories and data repositories across the different regions and institutions within the ERA, b) providing scholarships, fellowships and training programmes to attract and retain top talent from diverse backgrounds; c) promoting gender equality, diversity, and inclusion in STEM; and d) facilitating partnerships between universities, research institutes, industry, and other stakeholders.

Policy topic 2: Strengthening careers

Is there a need to develop a model tenure-track system at European level to contribute to solving precariousness of early career researchers? If you believe so, how do you think it should be structured? In light of the [policy process on the reform of assessment](#) of research and institutions, what are your recommendations on how to address academic/researcher career assessment?

Keep the process initiated by COARA. EELISA partners reiterate the messages included in D1.3, i.e. the question of developing a tenure-track system at European level awakes conflicting views among EELISA InnoCORE partners. Moreover, as highlighted in D1.3, EELISA partners reiterate that several aspects still need to be improved as previous steps. Having a tenure-track system at European level will require **having consistent standards of academic quality and accreditation across universities**, establishing common standards and criteria for mutual recognition and accreditation of qualification, credits, and research outputs, developing a framework for assessing and validating academic qualifications, harmonizing credit transfer systems, and defining criteria for evaluating research quality and impact. **The [policy process on the reform of assessment](#) is already working in this direction and the process is triggering changes in EU Member States.** As a concrete example, it is worth noting that ANECA (the National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation of Spain) modified very recently the Spanish accreditation model introducing changes aligned with the proposals of COARA. The modification of the system came into force on 1st April 2024, i.e. only some weeks ago from the drafting of this paper. The impact and transformation potential of the new system, including its potential contribution to building a European tenure-track, will only be clear in some years-time.

Policy topic 3: digital transition

What are the specific needs of the alliances to accelerate their digital transition in the R&I dimension, and how can this be addressed at the EU level? In particular, do you see a need for *additional* dedicated e-infrastructures for data storage and management that are distributed and interoperable? Please take into account progress regarding the development of the federated e-infrastructure for research outputs (EOSC, see [ERA Policy Agenda](#)), and the implementation of a digital platform for cooperation in higher education (see the [European strategy for universities](#)).

Keep promoting interoperability. As described above and in Policy Brief D1.3, progress and work done under InnoCORE and EELISA has revealed various challenges on the topic of digital transition, including very particularly interoperability. To the already pointed out recommendations and challenges, EELISA InnoCORE partners would like to recall that other Alliances are also creating IT tools and platforms with similar functions. Within this context, some EELISA partners wonder if it would not be appropriate having some IT solution at the scale of the European Commission, helping that these tools that are now working independently become interoperable. This might be done via some dedicated funding stream for inter-Alliance projects funding digital innovation hubs, technology demonstrators or strategic research agenda focused on digital transformation at inter-Alliance scale.

